

A Modular Concept for Quiet Zone Generation in Transportation Media with Multiple Seat Configurations*

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Abstract The main source of noise inside the passenger compartments of a broad class of transportation media (aircrafts, trains, buses, ships) stems from engine vibrations which are characterized by tonal low frequency content. Conventional passive noise control methods present limitations due to these low frequency components. Active noise control methods cannot cover broad spatial areas, due to the added noise effect of secondary loudspeakers. The proposed approach is based on a fundamental active noise cancellation block, which consists of a pair of loudspeakers for each passenger seat placed next to the left and right ear accordingly, aiming to generate a broad quiet zone around each passenger's head. Additionally, the proposed approach aims to minimize the effect of the secondary (ANC) loudspeakers, in areas away from their intended control action. Thus, the proposed approach is rather modular and able to be adapted to many possible multiple seat configurations in passenger compartments. The approach is verified in various multiple passenger seat configurations, including configurations of six passengers sitting in two groups of three seats, either adjacent, or facing each other or one in front of the other. In contrast to the classical approach, a modified methodology incorporating a linear, impedance based formulation is followed. The generated sound field is investigated along with the scattering effect of the heads of the passengers and finally the resulting quiet zones in the vicinity of the passengers' ears. The results indicate reductions of noise levels in these average quiet zones up to 15 dB, constituting a very promising foundation for real-time application of this ANC configuration.

Keywords: active noise control · noise cancellation · quiet zones · loudspeakers · aircraft acoustics

1 Introduction

The noise inside the compartments of the passengers in air and ground transportation media such as cars, aircraft, buses, trains etc., is generated by a number of sources including the motors, wheel or rail interfaces, aerodynamic loads and many others. A majority of these sources emit noise of variable frequency content, as is the case of the engine noise due to variations in the speed of rotation. Some of these sources may produce broad-spectrum and random noise, like aerodynamic loads and the flowing boundary layer for example, while others may be permanent or transient.

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In modern transportation media, the trend of continuously increasing the engine power, leads to equivalent increase in the levels of emitted noise. Simultaneously, the constant driving for weight reduction of their structural elements, constrains the utilization of conventional passive soundproofing means due to the fact that their performance is generally associated with increased mass and/or volume, especially at low frequencies e.g. below 500Hz, where they already present limited capabilities. Additionally, other solutions such as conventional passive vibration dampers have the ability to absorb at very specific frequencies, while they generally require additional masses.

Therefore, in order to adequately control these low-frequency content noise, an active noise control (ANC) integrated modular system is proposed. These types of active systems, present many advantages over classic passive systems, including the adaptability to the frequency content of the noise, the lower mass and compact size. In general, the primary objective of the ANC system (ANCS), is to generate a quiet zone around the head of a passenger at the headrest of a passenger seat, using local microphones and loudspeakers. Specifically, for the generation of a broader quiet zone in the examined application, the considered configuration has the form of Fig.1, where two driven loudspeakers and two corresponding microphones (cancellation points) are considered for each passenger. Regarding the formulation of the presented models used for the executed simulations, a 2D approach is taken, considering a x-y plane at the level of the ears of the passengers.

The target is a level of at least 10 [dB] noise reduction around the heads of six passengers, seated in two groups of three across each other, inside the cabin of a small business jet. The background noise inside the cabin is considered as having a distinct peak in the frequency spectrum at around 100 [Hz] and at noise levels of approximately 75 [dB], due to the rotational speed of the jet engines.

2 Primary Sound Field - Plane Wave Model

An acoustic field is considered to be perfectly diffuse in a volume, if the energy density is the same on all points of this volume. To generate a perfectly diffuse field the Plane Wave Model is used. In the general case, the sound field is a superposition of an infinite number of freely propagating plane waves, such that all directions of propagation are equally probable and the phase relation of the waves are random. The most commonly used techniques of diffuseness evaluation, meaning to characterize a diffuse field, are the cross-correlation and the spatial uniformity of the pressure field [6].

The spatial cross-correlation function of the pressure field between two points is expressed as

$$C(\kappa R) = Re\left(\frac{\overline{p(\mathbf{r})p(\mathbf{r} + \mathbf{r}')}}{\sqrt{\overline{p^2(\mathbf{r})}\overline{p^2(\mathbf{r} + \mathbf{r}')}}}\right) \quad (1)$$

where

$$R = |\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}'| \quad (2)$$

The analytic prediction, using the plane wave model, leads to

$$C(\kappa R) = \frac{\sin(\kappa R)}{\kappa R} \quad (3)$$

However it is known that a diffuse field cannot be established in a volume for a monochromatic source, a result not predicted by the plane-wave model. For a monochromatic source, one can show that the correlation function becomes 0 or ± 1 , which is also the case here [5].

Figure1: (a) The analytic prediction of the correlation function (b) Correlation function of the current model.

The primary sound field is simulated as a superposition of $K_{max} \times L_{max}$ plane waves

$$\tilde{p}(x_0, y_0, \kappa, t) = \hat{p} e^{-j\kappa d(x_0, y_0)} e^{j\omega t + \phi} \quad (4)$$

propagating from different directions. This approach corresponds to L_{max} plane waves coming from L_{max} different azimuthal directions at angles ϕ_L , ($L = 1, 2, \dots, L_{max}$), for each of the K_{max} vertical incident directions at angles θ_K , ($K = 1, 2, \dots, K_{max}$).

Therefore the mathematical formulation of the Plane Wave Model (PWM), leads to the following expression for the complex acoustic pressure of the primary field [7]:

$$\tilde{p}(x, y, t) = \sum_{K=1}^{K_{max}} \sum_{L=1}^{L_{max}} \hat{p} \sin \theta_k e^{j\phi} e^{j\kappa(x_0 \sin \theta_k \cos \phi_L + y_0 \sin \theta_k \sin \phi_L)} e^{j\omega t} \quad (5)$$

The factor $\sin \theta_k$ is included to ensure that, on average, the energy associated with the incident waves, is uniform from all directions. The amplitude \hat{p} of the complex acoustic pressure of the plane waves is calculated accordingly, in order to simulate a background diffuse sound field with an average of $L_{p_{tot}}$ 75 [dB] SPL. For each incident wave superimposed, the random coefficients a_{KL} and b_{KL} are defined via a random population with Gaussian distribution. Therefore the phase angle ϕ comes as $\phi = \arctan(-b_{KL}/a_{KL})$. The values of the coefficients a_{KL} and b_{KL} are determined from a random population with Gaussian distribution for mean value 0 and standard deviation 1 for the calculation of angle ϕ for each grid point.

Initially the main data for a specific frequency and the Sound Pressure Level of the primary field are set along with the geometry of the space where the simulation will take place. The main characteristics of the primary sound field are calculated as shown on Table 1.

The lengths L_x and L_y are the dimensions of the simulated space along the x and y axis accordingly. Next, the time average sound pressure and the SPL of this primary field are calculated. In the PWM, the complex acoustic pressure is calculated at every point on the computational grid. The simulation time is set to one period $T = 1/f_0$ and the time increment at $T/16$. Subsequently, the time average for one period T, of the acoustic pressure at each point, can be calculated, thus forming an average pressure distribution. The average primary field is calculated from twenty executions of the PWM and is used for the following simulations.

Figure 2: (a) Definition of spherical coordinates r , θ , ϕ , for an incident plane wave propagating along the direction of line r and the plane perpendicular to lines A and B and parallel to line r . (b) Primary diffuse sound field as generated by the PWM, used as the background noise.

Table 1: Sound and spatial parameters of primary sound field

f_0 [Hz]	$L_{p_{tot}}$	L_x	L_y	c_0 [m/s]	ρ_0 [kg/m ³]	ω [rad/sec]	κ	λ
100	75	1.9	2	340.290	1.225	628.319	1.846	3.403

3 Model of Head Interference

The diffusion caused in the primary sound field from the interference of the heads of the seated passengers has to be calculated, before implementing the active noise control. This interference is calculated as a superposition of spherical scatterers representing the heads and the primary sound field. A convenient way to handle a scattering problem is the approach as an equivalent radiation problem[2].

Thus, each spherical scatterer is modelled as a spherical source of the 2nd kind[3]

$$\hat{p}_{sc}(r, \phi, t) = \sum_{m=0}^{\infty} A_m h_m^{(2)}(\kappa r) P_m(\cos \phi) e^{j\omega t} \quad (6)$$

The coefficients of the vibrational pattern on the surface of the spherical scatterer come as

$$A_m = -j\omega\rho(\mathbf{Z}^H \mathbf{Z})^{-1} \mathbf{Z}^H \hat{\mathbf{u}}_{sc} \quad (7)$$

where the matrix \mathbf{Z} contains functions of Legendre polynomials and spherical Hankel functions of the 2nd kind, while the vector $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{sc}$, is calculated as $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{sc} = -\hat{\mathbf{u}}_{inc} = p_p(a)/\rho \cdot c_0$, where \mathbf{u}_{sc} , \mathbf{u}_{inc} is the radial particle velocity of the scattering and the incident sound field accordingly, at the surface of the spherical scatterer and a is the radius of the spherical scatterer (head).

Assuming that each head approximately rests on the plane of the secondary sources (speakers), an approximate radius of the heads $r_{hd} \approx 0.1$ [m] is considered, which is translated to grid intervals. The superposition of the interference from each head is implemented utilizing the incident time average sound pressure field.

It should be noted that in order for the generated \mathbf{Z} matrix not being ill-conditioned (large condition number, almost singular matrix), the number of considered points on the surface of the spherical scatterer and consequently the dimensions of \mathbf{Z} , \hat{u}_{sc} and A_m , need to be around ten times bigger than the number (M) of the Legendre-Hankel terms used for the modeling of the scatterer[7]. To avoid reconstructing a much denser computational grid in order to achieve such a number of sample points on the surface of the head, a mean value for the scattering particle velocity is calculated from the existing sample points instead. The interference of the head is then superimposed on the initial sound field. This approximation does not insert considerable error, since the frequency in this case is low ($k\alpha < 1$), thus the aforementioned velocity vector and consequently the A_m coefficients do not change considerably from head to head.

4 Model of Driven Loudspeakers

After superimposing the interference from the heads of the passengers to the primary diffuse field, it is possible to calculate the required volume velocity of the driven loudspeakers in order to generate the desired quiet zones around the heads of the passengers.

The total complex pressure of each sound field point assuming linear superposition, is calculated as[2]

$$\tilde{p}(\mathbf{r}) = \tilde{p}_p(\mathbf{r}) + \tilde{p}_s(\mathbf{r}) \quad (8)$$

The sound pressure of the secondary field generated from a loudspeaker is

$$\tilde{p}_s(\mathbf{r}) = Z_d(\mathbf{r}|\mathbf{r}_s)q_s(\mathbf{r}_s) \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{r}_s is the position vector of the center of the loudspeaker.

Modeling each driven loudspeaker as a circular piston in an infinite rigid baffle and considering the "on axis" approximation for the radiated transfer impedance field, derived from the Rayleigh integral for points lying along the axis of the piston motion[3], gives

$$Z_d(\mathbf{r}|\mathbf{r}_s) = \frac{\rho_0 c_0}{S} \left(e^{-j\kappa r} - e^{-j\kappa \sqrt{r^2 + R^2}} \right) \quad (10)$$

where $Z_d(\mathbf{r}|\mathbf{r}_s)$ is the direct free space transfer impedance that would be generated by the secondary source in the absence of reflecting boundaries (negligible reverberant secondary impedance field Z_r for such low frequencies), $r = |\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}_s|$ is the distance between a point in the sound field and the center of the circular piston and R is the radius of the circular piston.

Here, the circular piston is considered to oscillate harmonically in a rigid baffle of infinite extent to ensure against the interference from backward scattered sound. Furthermore, it is assumed that all points on the face of the piston oscillate with the same phase. Since the frequency of the primary field is relatively low, this assumptions provide an accurate enough insight into the typical size of the quiet zones achievable.

4.1 Optimal Volume Velocity

The basic approach of an ANC system, is to drive the sound pressure to zero at a selected cancellation point:

$$\tilde{p}(\mathbf{r}) = \tilde{p}_p(\mathbf{r}) + \tilde{p}_s(\mathbf{r}) = 0 \quad (11)$$

therefore

$$\tilde{p}_s(\mathbf{r}) = -\tilde{p}_p(\mathbf{r}) = Z_d(\mathbf{r}|\mathbf{r}_s)q_s(\mathbf{r}_s) \quad (12)$$

Thus, an optimal secondary source (driven loudspeaker) volume velocity has to be calculated as follows[4]:

$$q_{so} = -\frac{\tilde{p}_{cp}}{Z_d(\mathbf{r}_{cp}|\mathbf{r}_s)} \quad (13)$$

where \mathbf{r}_{cp} is the position vector of the cancellation point, p_{cp} is the sound pressure at the cancellation point and q_{so} is the optimal volume velocity of the driven loudspeaker.

Revised Method - "Lean" ANC Instead of attempting to achieve total noise cancellation at a selected cancellation point as in the classical approach, the ratio of primary to final sound pressure for a 10 [dB] noise reduction at the cancellation points is calculated.

$$20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\tilde{p}(\mathbf{r})}{p_{ref}} \right) - 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\tilde{p}_p(\mathbf{r})}{p_{ref}} \right) = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\tilde{p}(\mathbf{r})}{\tilde{p}_p(\mathbf{r})} \right) = -10 [dB] \quad (14)$$

which leads to $\tilde{p}(\mathbf{r})/\tilde{p}_p(\mathbf{r}) = 10^{-1/2} = 0.3162$. Therefore the sound pressure generated by the secondary source at the cancellation point comes as

$$\tilde{p}_s(\mathbf{r}) = -0.6838 \tilde{p}_p(\mathbf{r}) = Z_d(\mathbf{r}|\mathbf{r}_s)q_s(\mathbf{r}_s) \quad (15)$$

The reasoning behind this approach is that this way, the volume velocity of each loudspeaker would be enough to achieve the desired 10 [dB] quiet zone without being high enough to increase the final sound pressure elsewhere in the field causing ineffectiveness of the noise cancellation configuration in total.

Furthermore, taking into account the interaction between all the driven loudspeakers at each cancellation point for the calculation of the optimal volume velocities, the direct impedance from the center of each driven loudspeaker to each cancellation point is considered. Thus, the sound pressure at each cancellation point comes as:

$$\tilde{p}_{cp,i} = -\frac{1}{0.6838} \left[q_{so,1} Z_d(\mathbf{r}_i|\mathbf{r}_{s1}) + q_{so,2} Z_d(\mathbf{r}_i|\mathbf{r}_{s2}) + \dots + q_{so,n} Z_d(\mathbf{r}_i|\mathbf{r}_{sn}) \right] \quad (16)$$

where

- $i=1,2,\dots,n$ cancellation points (and driven speakers),
- \mathbf{r}_{si} : position vector of the center of the i -th loudspeaker,
- \mathbf{r}_i : position vector of the i -th cancellation point,
- $p_{cp,i}$: sound pressure at the i -th cancellation point,
- $q_{so,i}$: optimal volume velocity of the i -th driven loudspeaker.

Consequently, a linear system is formed for the n number of loudspeakers in each case, from where the vector containing their volume velocities, comes as:

$$\{\mathbf{q}_{so}\}_{n \times 1} = -0.6838 [\mathbf{Z}_d(\mathbf{r}|\mathbf{r}_s)]_{n \times n}^{-1} \{\mathbf{p}_{cp}\}_{n \times 1} \quad (17)$$

5 Results

5.1 Computational Grid

The $L_x \times L_y$ computational grid on the y-x plane of the space is created considering $M = N = 100$ grid points on the x and y axis accordingly, as noted on Fig. 3. Figure 3 also demonstrates the geometrical parameters of the basic configuration for each passenger, namely two loudspeakers at each headrest with two corresponding cancellation points at distance α from the center of the loudspeaker.

Figure 3: Geometry of the computational grid and the active control system. Notation for a single head – two driven loudspeakers configuration.

5.2 Extent and Interaction of Quiet Zones

In order to simulate the operational principle of an ANC configuration, a driven loudspeaker-microphone (cancellation point) pair is considered. Figure 4.a shows the difference between the initial and the final sound field as a result of the ANC system. Also a more detailed look is presented in Fig. 4.b in the form of the generated average quiet zone. Here, the dimensions are normalized to the distance α .

Furthermore, the extent or in other words the diameter of the quiet zone and its shape, depend among others on the aforementioned distance α . The effect of this parameter is showcased in Fig. 5. A general conclusion is that increasing the distance α is shrinking the quiet zone while at the same time reduces the effectiveness of the ANC configuration in terms of noise reduction [4]. In this particular application, the loudspeakers will be placed at the two ends of the space that is being examined. It is assumed that these boundaries do not cause any reflections therefore they are neglected in this simulation.

Figure 4: (a) The difference of SPL between the initial and the final sound field. (b) Typical shape of an average quiet zone on the x-y plane.

Figure 5: Alteration of quiet zone as a function of distance α . For $R =$ loudspeaker radius: (a) $\alpha \approx 1.5 R$ (b) $\alpha \approx 3.8 R$ (c) $\alpha \approx 7.5 R$

Next, the examination of the sound pressure distribution of a driven loudspeaker, modeled as a circular piston in an infinite rigid baffle, with the appropriate volume velocity for each approach is presented. Comparison between Figs. 6.a and 6.b demonstrate the advantage of the revised approach as the SPL at the far field of the loudspeaker is significantly lower. Keeping in mind the final configuration of six passengers with twelve corresponding driven loudspeakers, it is obviously expected that the rise of SPL in the spatial area outside the controlled quiet zones is going to be much more pronounced while also affecting the levels of noise reduction inside the quiet zones themselves.

Figure 6: SPL [dB] of the sound field on the x-y plane generated by a circular piston in an infinite rigid baffle. (a) Full ANC (b) Lean ANC.

One Passenger The next step in the simulation procedure, is the addition of the interference of a spherical scatterer representing the head of a passenger, along with two side-by-side driven loudspeakers mounted behind the head. Considering the extent of the quiet zone generated by a driven loudspeaker around a cancellation point as seen in Fig. 5.a, the cancellation points are chosen between the ears and the center of each loudspeaker. This case examines the possibility of generating an extended quiet zone along the y-axis by using two driven loudspeakers side-by-side instead of one. It is observed that the objective of extending the quiet zone is successful this way. The average quiet zones of each loudspeaker are essentially superimposed extending the range of the final quiet zone. These results, showcase the first encouraging signs towards the improvement of the overall efficiency of the system. Figure 7, demonstrate that despite the lower volume velocity, the -10 dB quiet zone around the head is achieved with satisfactory extent, while the rise of the sound level at the opposite side and the rest of the field in general, is almost insignificant.

Figure 7.a shows the difference between the SPL of the final sound field and the primary sound field. The final sound field is a result of linear superposition of the sound pressure distribution by the driven loudspeaker and the primary sound field. Figure 7.b shows the form of the generated zone of quiet in the proximity of the cancellation points and around the head of a single passenger. In this configuration, it is obvious that the interference of the head at such low frequencies [1], does not affect whatsoever the efficiency of the active noise control setup when comparing Figs. 5.a and 5.b.

Figure 7: (a) Difference between the SPL [dB] of the final sound field and the primary sound field. (b) Average generated quiet zone at the proximity of the head of one passenger.

Two Opposite Passengers For further examination, more passengers are gradually added in the spatial area of the simulation in order to examine any efficiency drop at each step. This scenario, examines the case of two passengers opposite to each other. Here, the aim is to examine the interaction between two sets of driven loudspeakers, positioned at the two opposite sides of the cabin and investigate possible complications due to rise of the SPL in the far field of the opposite driven loudspeakers. The results presented in Fig. 8, do not indicate any significant negative effects regarding the level of noise reduction and the extent and uniformity of the -10 dB quiet zones.

Figure 8: (a) The difference between the final Sound Pressure Level [dB] of the field on the x-y plane and the primary sound field. (b) The generated quiet zones at the proximity of each cancellation point and around the passengers' heads.

Three Adjacent Passengers Following is the examination of the side-by-side interaction of the noise control configuration when three passengers are seated on the same side of the cabin. This amounts to a total of six loudspeakers at the same end of the space. Observation of Fig. 9, shows that the rising number of headrests and consequently their corresponding loudspeakers, added to

the initial sound field, begin to affect the degree of noise cancellation and especially the extend of the generated -10 dB quiet zones around the heads of the passengers. Nevertheless, the target level of noise reduction is still comfortably achievable.

Figure9: (a) The difference between the SPL [dB] of the final field and the primary sound field. (b) Average generated quiet zones at one side of the cabin for a configuration for three passengers.

Six Passengers Finally, the configuration of interest concerning six seated passengers, three on each side is examined. This results to a total of six pairs of driven loudspeakers. The enhancement of the active noise control configuration using the revised approach, is crystal clear in this final comparison. Observation of Fig.10.b, shows that the target of 10 [dB] noise reduction is achievable and the extent of the quiet zones covers the desired area around the heads of the passengers. Also, Fig.10.a shows that although the increase of the SPL in the far field of the driven loudspeakers at the intermediate space is perceivable, it can be considered that the "Lean" approach successfully manages to achieve the target level of noise reduction without significant side effects.

Figure 10: (a) The difference between the final Sound Pressure Level [dB] of the field on the x-y plane and the primary sound field. (b) The generated quiet zones at the proximity of each cancellation point and around the passengers' heads.

6 Experimental Setup

For a preliminary investigation of an experimental ANC system, a configuration of three adjacent passengers and one at the opposite end has been set up, as shown in Fig. 11.a. The positions of the error microphones for each of the two loudspeakers of every headrest are indicated on Fig. 11.a by the red "x" symbols. These microphones measure the sound pressure at these points and these signals act as the feedback to an LMS algorithm loop using the LabVIEW® software for the calculation and generation of the canceling sound signal of the loudspeakers. The control law of this loop imposed by an external amplifier regarding the power of the loudspeakers -hence the amplitude of the generated canceling signal- is defined by the same methodology applied in the precedent simulations.

Figure 11.b presents indicative measurements from the right error microphone of the middle seat B, before and after the activation of the active noise control. The red dots indicate the peak at 100 [Hz]. The SPL at this frequency after the activation of the ANC, shows a ≈ 16 [dB] reduction from 71 to 55 [dB]. This level of reduction is approximately observed for the rest of the headrests too.

Figure 11: (a) Experimental setup configuration. (b) Noise spectrum at middle seat before and after active noise cancellation.

7 Conclusions

The revised approach, successfully tackles the issues of ineffectiveness of the control due to the rise of the total sound pressure caused by the high number of driven loudspeakers with unnecessary high volume velocities. Additionally, it is obvious that the linear impedance based calculation of the volume velocities, generates an almost perfectly uniform distribution of the quiet zones between the opposite sides of the cabin and at the same time corresponds to a practical implementation in a real world, active noise control configuration. The summary of the results regarding the simulated cases, is that, such an active noise control method in the desired configuration of six passengers is feasible. However, the establishment of the desired -10 [dB] quiet zones at the left and right edges of the space is marginal, although, the procedure followed does not include any feedback for adaptive calculation of the corresponding optimal volume velocities as would be the case in a real time

ANCS. The measurements performed with the experimental setup utilizing feedback closed-loop algorithms, are generally in line with the simulations and at the same time do not demonstrate any performance drop for the left and right side passengers.

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